

M5 Validation of didactical methods for curriculum & training

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summarising the knowledge from the whole IP4OS consortium

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List of abbreviations

FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable principles
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IP4OS	Intellectual Property for Open Science (Horizon Europe project)
OER	Open Educational Resource
OS	Open Science
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
TDM	Text and Data Mining

Summary

IP4OS promotes **knowledge valorisation** by linking **intellectual property (IP)** management and **open science (OS)** practices. The curriculum designed for the IP4OS training focuses on core content, including **multi-perspective competences, minimal skills, awareness of reliable Knowledge Valorisation, and effectively teaching Knowledge Valorisation** and innovative didactical methods, such as a **dialogue- and engagement-based approach**.

The training focuses on participants' real application domains, encouraging them to **test, co-create, and reflect** on practices that drive **institutional change** and combines **dialogue and real-case learning** to make complex IP–OS interactions tangible. The approach has two layers:

1. **Pilot Learning Lab** – a three-session, action-based sprint where institutions form multi-professional teams to test collaboration, map roles, and co-create procedures for institutional valorisation strategies.
2. **Profession-Specific Deepening** – self-paced learning using dialogue-based expert panel recordings and reflection exercises tailored to different roles (e.g., librarians, data stewards, research managers, Knowledge Technology Transfer professionals and researchers).

Together, these layers strengthen teamwork, professional expertise, and institutional mechanisms, turning knowledge valorisation into a **shared and strategic practice** rather than a compliance task.

1. Guiding Principles

In June 2025, experts highlighted important principles ([Alavi, M. et al., 2025](#)) in knowledge valorisation, demonstrating how teaching IP and OS is a crucial element for knowledge valorisation and can be effectively designed.

- **Knowledge valorisation requires multi-perspective competences:** building capacity in IP and OS is not only about knowledge but also about learning to view knowledge valorisation practices from different professions and viewpoints. Following the expert's explanations (see [Hermannsdörfer, N., & Prieß-Buchheit, J., 2021](#)), developing multi-perspective competences means learning to shift perspectives, explain reasoning clearly, and accept that different answers can coexist. It involves building shared understanding in discussions, comparing, and finding alternative solutions.
These skills prepare learners for cross-sectoral collaboration, which is central to a synergetic IP–OS approach. Such multi-perspective competences include using perspective shifts in conversation, combining and evaluating different approaches while accepting plurality, applying communication to solve complex problems, recognising the challenges of siloed professions, valuing the importance of multi-perspective exchange, and appreciating insights that come from looking beyond one's own field.
- **Knowledge Valorisation requires the following minimal skills:** deciding whether to focus on producing or reusing intellectual assets, determining when and for how long assets should be shared or protected, identifying which IPRs are most suitable, and understanding how open outputs should be managed. (This can be displayed in

a simple knowledge valorisation rubric containing the categories Producing vs. Using Assets / Timing / Level of Reuse)

- **Knowledge Valorisation needs to raise awareness of reliable knowledge exploitation:** demonstrating, through real cases, why compliance is essential and how it strengthens the process.
- **Teaching Knowledge Valorisation in an effective manner:** Recognising that many seemingly difficult cases in applying IPR in an OS context can be addressed and solved with improved knowledge, awareness, and the right tools, and at the same time acknowledging that dilemma methods are not the right didactical tool for that.

In general, learning through play fits the above and creates a playful setting where people from different backgrounds, professions, and skill levels can explore the complex practice of knowledge valorisation. This playful atmosphere lowers barriers, encourages dialogue, and helps participants discuss knowledge valorisation through IP and OS openly. Well-designed sessions become a flow experience in which learning feels natural, enjoyable, and effective ([Alavi, M. et al. 2025](#)).

Taking this into account, IP4OS follows a **dialogical and engagement-based approach**. Training is co-created with different professions and multi-professional teams and starts with the target group's specific needs. Learners do not just attend; they test, co-create, and reflect on real practices that lead to institutional change. Learning is structured in two layers: (1) the **Pilot Learning Lab**, a team-level experiential sprint, and (2) **Profession-Specific Deepening**, self-paced learning supported by recorded expert discussions.

2. Establishing Multi-Professional Teams through the IP4OS Pilot Learning Lab

The Pilot Learning Lab is a 3-session, action-oriented sprint designed to help institutions set up and test their multi-professional teams.

Structure of the Lab (3 x 2h sessions + fieldwork in between):

- **Session 1: Roles, Realities & Friction Points**
 - Explore why multi-professional teams are needed now.
 - Clarify each role's benefits, responsibilities, and potential friction points (e.g., IP vs. OS timing conflicts).
 - Begin role-mapping and mini-case exercises.
- **Between Session 1 & 2:** Mini Field Test (e.g., try out a structured discussion in a real project).
- **Session 2: Communication & Collaboration**
 - Scenario simulations (e.g., conflict between preprint and patent filing).
 - Reflection on collaboration dynamics and shared pain points.
 - Co-create principles for teamwork and internal consultation services.
- **Between Session 2 & 3:** Micro-reporting (short reflection on what was tested and what worked/failed).
- **Session 3: Transfer & Implementation**

- From insights to institutional change: draft the first Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and identify enablers/barriers.
- Co-create actionable next steps for institutional adoption.
- Teams report back and contribute insights to the IP4OS Synergy Framework.

Key Features:

- Not “one more training,” but a **safe-to-fail space** to experiment and adjust.
- Focus on **institutional mechanisms** rather than individual learning.
- Concrete outputs: an effective multi-professional team able to consult researchers, fostering knowledge valorisation

Continuous reflection:

- The concept includes continuous reflection on whether the multi-professional team create time-efficient pathways and mobility/peer-learning touchpoints for the participants—two gaps repeatedly flagged in the [Research Managers ROADMAP survey results](#)?

3. Training Professions: Dialogical Engagement & Profession-Specific Deepening

In parallel to the Pilot Lab, IP4OS adds a **second training layer**: profession-specific strengthening.

Method:

- **Recorded Expert Panels:** Moderated discussions on pressing topics (e.g., copyright in TDM, OS collaboration in patent-heavy fields, rights retention strategies). Captured as Open Educational Resources (OERs) for reuse and enhanced with monologues from IP4OS role models and testimonials.
- **Fishbowl Format:** The recorded expert discussion forms the inner circle of learning. Around this core, learners engage through short, guided exercises that connect directly to the recording. These prompts help participants reflect on the content and apply it to their own institutional and professional context.
- **Guiding Questions:** Each profession receives tailored reflection prompts for self-paced learning, for example:
 - *Librarians:* How can I support researchers in secondary publication rights?
 - *Data Stewards:* Which licences fit FAIR data reuse in my field?
 - *Research Managers:* How do I integrate IP–OS strategies into grant proposals?

Didactical Flow:

- **Dialogue in the Pilot Lab** ensures a strong team foundation.
- **Self-paced reflection** via recorded fishbowl sessions deepens professional expertise.
- **Feedback loop:** professionals bring back their insights into the team context, strengthening collaborative problem-solving.

4. Expected Outcomes

- **Stronger Teams:** Teams co-design their working mode, tailored to their institution.
- **Empowered Professions:** Each profession strengthens its expertise through targeted reflection and self-paced learning.
- **Sustainable Resources:** FAIR recordings and guiding questions for each learning unit.
- **Institutional Change:** Knowledge valorisation moves from compliance to a **shared, strategic practice**.

References

Alavi, M., Errington, T., Miller, K., Morrison, C., Priess-Buchheit, J. C., Secker, J., & Sharma, G., 2025. Teaching & Learning Report for Intellectual Property and Open Science. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17069794>

Hermannsdörfer, N., & Prieß-Buchheit, J. (2021). Interdisziplinäre Handlungsfähigkeit. *Zeitschrift für Hochschulentwicklung*, 16(3), 181–198. <https://doi.org/10.3217/zfhe-16-03/11>